

Assessment Of Factors Affecting Students' Learning Attitude: A Case Study In Some Public Universities In Ho Chi Minh City

Lan Chi Le, Thai Dinh Do

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 28, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 23, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Student, Attitude, Learning, Public, University, Ho Chi Minh City, SGU</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5129136</p>	<p><i>Higher education plays an important role in providing knowledge and skills for students to enter the labour market. In the current context of globalization and international integration, it is necessary to have students with a lifelong learning attitude. Therefore, the main objective of this paper is to find out the factors affecting the students' learning attitude in public schools in Ho Chi Minh City. The authors randomly sampled data and evaluated the reliability of the assessment scale using Cronbach's Alpha, performed Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) and checked the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). In addition, the authors surveyed 540 students studying at 6 universities each of which has about 90 students answering 29 questions. The research has shown that there are 6 factors affecting the students' learning attitude in public universities in Ho Chi Minh City. Based on the findings, the authors have proposed recommendations to enhance the positive attitude of students in public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.</i></p>

Introduction

Today, we are living in an era of information explosion with a stronger development of science and technology than ever before. With an increasingly rich and diverse amount of knowledge, the urge for improving critical thinking is infinite, but an individual's life is limited by space and time. Learning time at school is limited. The amount of knowledge that is applied by a learner is only about 20% of the amount of knowledge that is taught. The gap of 80% is caused by the fact that there are many skills and knowledge required in real-world problems that cannot be learnt from school (Le et al, 2020). Learning is a self-directed process for a student to acquire wisdom (i.e., no one can learn for someone else). Learning attitude not only plays an essential role in the quality of learning but also affects the personality development of students (Solovetrich, 1975). Therefore, the authors chose to study factors that affect students' learning attitude, thereby making recommendations to improve students' learning attitude in universities. It helps lecturers improve the teaching quality and helps schools improve training efficiency.

Literature Review

Learning attitude (LA)

The nature of learning activities is an active cognitive process. Students want to gain knowledge of mankind. To survive and develop in the fast-paced economy, students themselves must stay on top of the labour market, nurture the desire to gain knowledge, be resilient to overcome all difficulties (Carroll, 1992). Students' positive learning attitude in the learning process will help them find knowledge on their own, and find a suitable learning method for themselves (Michael, 2004). Students with a good study attitude will actively create a study plan and find a suitable learning method for themselves, which helps students achieve good results (Burke and Williams, 2008). In addition, with a positive learning attitude, they will try to explore other topics related to the subject being taught (Kara, 2010).

Learning is an activity that each individual must strive for and must have goals so that learners can achieve the desired results (Giordon, 2008). From the point of view of scientists, a good student is someone who has a good motivation to study and has a positive attitude towards learning. If learners do not arrange their study plans, motivation will decrease and thus academic success will be difficult to achieve (Park, 2003). In a study done by Burke & Williams, it was found that students who are well motivated to learn are more successful in their studies and have study skills (Burke & Williams, 2008). In addition, when students have a learning attitude, they will make an enormous effort in finding knowledge in subjects (Kara, 2010). Learning is an individual effort. Positive or negative attitudes will affect learning and contribute to the success or failure of learning.

School factor (SF)

Providing good quality education requires universities to have adequate facilities such as: Classrooms, laboratories, human resources, teachers and support staff. They play an important role in the study process of students (Mbatia, 2004). Some authors have studied and pointed out the impact of the learning environment on learners' learning attitudes. If the learning environment is fully equipped, it will create favourable conditions for learners (Mayama, 2012; Lumuli, 2009). Some researchers have identified facilities and teaching equipment as factors that contribute to the learning quality of learners in schools (Dinh et al., 2018).

In addition, the curriculum plays a crucial role related to the learning attitude of the learners. A training program should be designed based on the learner's capacity and the needs of society (Jenkins, 1994). Besides, organizational factors inside the school such as the management of school activities contribute to the quality of education and this will lead to learners' attitudes (Digolo, 2003; Eshiwani, 1993).

Hypothesis H1: The school factor has a positive influence on the students' learning attitude in public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

Lecturer factor (LF)

The close interrelationship between the teacher's external influence expressed in the presentation of materials, the program, the organization of student learning and the problem-solving part from the learners' side affects the learning attitudes of learners (Kharlamov, 1979). The teacher factor plays a critical role in the learning process of learners, a study by author Gurpreet Kaur shows that teaching methods will effectively affect learners' learning through factors such as: thoughtful planning for teaching, flexible teaching methods suitable for subjects; lecturers have a way of conveying information that is easy to understand and attractive (Gurpreet Kaur, 2011). Through the optimal use of teaching methods, it will increase the positive learning attitude and improve the learning quality of learners. Instructors play an important role in enhancing learners' positive learning attitudes. If teachers design their curriculum carefully, apply teaching methods facilitating discussion and study groups in the teaching process, it will create excitement in learning (Raditya, 2017).

Hypothesis H2: The lecturer factor has a positive influence on the students' learning attitude in public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

Family factor (FF)

Family support is an important factor influencing student learning attitudes (Cabrera et al., 1993). The family factor is one of the key factors that lay the foundation for learners to overcome learning difficulties (West et al. 1985). Some learners fail to achieve their learning goals in the absence of family support and concern. Family can be a great supportive asset or a source of encouragement to relieve stress for learners when they face difficulties in their learning (Terenzini, 1992).

Parents influence learners' attitudes a lot. Active families that have positive lifestyles help learners have the right attitudes in learning. Motivation from family helps learners develop personality (Shaffer, 2005). To see if learners' attitudes are good, some researchers have proposed to observe the dynamics of their families (Relvas & Vaz, 2007). Several studies have shown that the most important role of the family is to shape their morality, family is their first experience with familiar relationships. Therefore, the family plays an important role in the development of social skills (Laible et al., 2004).

Hypothesis H3: The family factor has a positive influence on the students' learning attitude in public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

Career prospects (CP)

Career is the goal of each learner when they choose their majors in university (Ambrose & Kulik, 1999). Researchers have also studied a lot about the relationship between career prospects and student motivation. Students are often more interested in majors that help them find a stable job, obviously, that profession must be suitable for their ability (Pinder, 1998). Career prospects after graduation are related to learners' attitudes (Weinstein, 1998).

Hypothesis H4: The career prospects have a positive influence on the students' learning attitude in public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

Learning needs (LN)

Learning needs affect learners' learning attitudes through internal thinking and external influences

(Russell & Barrett, 1999). The difference in positive and negative attitudes expressed through emotions. The proper learning needs will help learners have a positive learning attitude. Pekrun (2006) has shown the importance of learning needs towards learning positive attitudes. A positive learning attitude will motivate learners to overcome all difficulties to achieve academic success. In contrast, negative attitudes are associated with fear of learning risks and reduce the concentration of learners. Positive attitudes are created by positive teacher-student relationships and a positive school environment (Fredrickson, 2001). In addition, the need to study well will create a good motivation to learn and create a good study attitude (Roeser et al., 1996).

Hypothesis H5: The learning needs have a positive influence on the students' learning attitude in public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

Learners' capacity (LC)

Learners with good learning ability will have methods and techniques to help absorb lessons more easily. Active learning comes from learning rooted in the natural efforts of learners; different individuals have different learning methods (Evan, 1999). Learners' learning needs can change. Nowadays, there is an explosion of knowledge that learners need to know what they need to learn and how to make the learning process easier (Kara, 2010). Today, learners are learning how to learn, make an effort to learn and continuously work towards focal points. In that context, learners need learning competencies to develop expectations of academic success. Learning to learn is being able to create new knowledge for new situations based on existing knowledge (Taşpınar, 2009). The ability to learn is the most important way for students to access knowledge. Competent learners will know how to solve problems they face (Saban, 2000). The learner's abilities affect the learner's learning attitude. If a learner has good capacity, he/she will learn easily to overcome difficulties and challenges in learning. It also helps learners have a positive attitude in receiving information, open to learning and have higher expectations in learning (Şen, 2013).

Hypothesis H6: The learner capacity has a positive influence on the students' learning attitude in public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

(Source: Researcher discovered)

Figure 1. A research model for factors affecting students' learning attitudes

METHODS OF RESEARCH

In this paper, the authors use a combination of two research methodologies which are qualitative and quantitative (figure 2). Two research methods are summarized in the 11 most basic research stages related to the assessment of factors affecting students' learning attitudes in public universities in Ho Chi Minh City as follows:

Stage 1 (Research title): The title of the thesis is to evaluate the factors affecting the learning attitude of research students in some public universities in Ho Chi Minh City. This study is usually selected based on the

actual situation of universities.

Stage 2 (Research Objectives): The authors must find out the objective of the research. The objective of the study is to evaluate the factors affecting the learning attitude of case study students in some public universities in Ho Chi Minh City. Based on the experiment, the authors propose recommendations to improve the students' learning attitude in some public universities in Ho Chi Minh City (Hair et al., 1998).

Stage 3 (Understanding the theories and studies relevant to the research): authors must find the research theories that are relevant to the research. This stage helps the authors build a model to evaluate the factors affecting the students' learning attitude.

Stage 4 (Building a preliminary assessment tool): The authors build a model for the preliminary assessment of factors affecting the learning attitude of case study students in some public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

Stage 5 (Qualitative research): The authors interview experts in educational subjects. The authors have built preliminaries based on 40 opinions from education experts to improve the model and the design of questions. The authors consulted 40 experts in the field of education, and all of them agreed with the factors affecting the learning attitude of case study students in some public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

Stage 6 (Adjusting the research model): This stage helps the model get better (Hair et al., 1998).

Stage 7 (Preliminary survey): The authors conducted a preliminary survey and assessed the reliability with Cronbach's Alpha coefficient and factor analysis. The authors surveyed 100 lecturers in 2 public universities in Ho Chi Minh City. This stage helps to improve the survey questionnaire (Hair et al., 1998).

Stage 8 (Quantitative study n = 540 students): The authors continued to survey 540 students. They are attending six public universities using survey questionnaires. Cronbach's Alpha coefficient is used to ensure the scale reliability. There are 6 public universities in Ho Chi Minh City that participated, each of which has about 90 to 100 students. There were 29 items surveyed and 540 students responded and the data was collected from October 2020 to March 2021.

Stage 9 (Cronbach's Alpha, Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) review): The authors used a random sampling technique and spent 25 minutes on one survey. The scale reliability is supported by Cronbach's Alpha coefficient. Next, the authors continued with CFA.

Stage 10 (Official research results): The authors tested the SEM model based on the results of stage 9.

Stage 11 (Conclusions and recommendations): The authors analyzed research data and proposed policies to improve the learning attitudes of students studying in some public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

(Source: Authors proposed)

Figure 2: The evaluation process of factors affecting learning attitudes of case study students in some public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

RESEARCH RESULTS

The authors have proposed research factors affecting the students' learning attitude in public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

A total of 540 students from 6 public universities in Ho Chi Minh City participated in the survey. Table 1 shows 29 observed variables and all values that have significant Cronbach's alpha coefficients. The data on the table is suitable and reliable for the next processing step. 29 variables are divided into 7 components, such as: (1) School factor; (2) Lecturer factor; (3) Career prospects; (4) Family factor; (5) Learning attitude; (6) Learning needs; and (7) Learners' capacity.

Table 1
THE SCALE RELIABILITY TESTS FOR FACTORS AFFECTING STUDENTS' LEARNING
ATTITUDES IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN HO CHI MINH CITY

Code	Content	Cronbach's Alpha
Cronbach's Alpha for School Factor (SF)		0.877
SF1	Good quality of classrooms	0.862
SF2	Fully equipped learning equipment for teaching	0.824
SF3	Safe, healthy and friendly educational environment	0.826
SF4	Rich textbooks and library materials	0.775
Cronbach's Alpha for Lecturer Factor (LF)		0.882
LF1	Instructors with extensive professional knowledge	0.889
LF2	Teaching methods that create positive feelings for students	0.845
LF3	Do teachers use teaching aids?	0.837
LF4	The lecturer provides many materials for students to study on their own	0.827
LF5	Teachers evaluate fairly and objectively	0.877
Cronbach's Alpha for Family Factor (FF)		0.850
FF1	Families have career guidance for their children	0.804
FF2	The family has a good background of knowledge and culture	0.783
FF3	The family has a good education method	0.838
FF4	Family monitors and timely provides support for children	0.741
Cronbach's Alpha for Career Prospects (CP)		0.873
CP1	Opportunity to easily find a job after graduation	0.887
CP2	Career with good prospects for the future	0.832
CP3	The profession requires more and more advanced knowledge	0.821
CP4	Understand the place and role of education in a career	0.803
Cronbach's Alpha for Learning Attitude (LA)		0.864
LA1	Actively set clear goals for yourself	0.821
LA2	Actively make study plans	0.932
LA3	Actively listen to the lecture and take notes in class carefully and revise	0.766
LA4	Actively discuss with the teacher about the issues that are not understood	0.811
Cronbach's Alpha for Learning Needs (LN)		0.873
LN1	The need to meet the expectations of loved ones	0.884
LN2	The need to acquire knowledge	0.835
LN3	The need to be respected by everyone	0.820
LN4	The need for promotion and high salary in the future	0.807
Cronbach's Alpha for Learners' Capacity (LC)		0.843
LC1	Ability to analyze and synthesize	0.833
LC2	Problem-solving ability	0.870
LC3	Critical thinking	0.757
LC4	Self-study	0.746

The results of Table 1 related to the reliability assessment of Cronbach's Alpha of each group of factors show that: (1) The school factor has Cronbach's Alpha of 0.877; (2) The lecturer factor has Cronbach's Alpha of 0.882; (3) The career prospects factor has Cronbach's Alpha of 0.877; (4) The family factor has Cronbach's Alpha of 0.850; (5) The learning attitude has Cronbach's Alpha of 0.864; (6) The learning needs factor has Cronbach's Alpha of 0.877; and (7) The learners' capacity factor has Cronbach's Alpha of 0.843. Most of the factors have good values (> 0.74).

After evaluating the reliability of the scale using Cronbach's Alpha, the authors conducted EFA. Table 2 shows the results of EFA of the remaining components in the study including 29 variables divided into 7 groups. The scale shows 7 variables indicating the factors affecting students' learning attitudes. The research team continues to use CFA analysis (Confirmatory Factor Analysis) to confirm once again the reliability of the EFA results. Factor Loading at ± 0.7 : The observed variables are statistically significant; Factor Loading at ± 0.5 : The observed variables are statistically significant; Factor Loading at ± 0.3 : The minimum conditions for the observed variable to be retained are met. The observation in Table 2 shows that the coefficients ≥ 0.5 , which indicates that the observed variables are statistically significant and meet the set objectives (Hair et al., 2009).

Table 2

**KMO AND BARTLETT'S TESTING FACTORS AFFECTING
STUDENTS' LEARNING ATTITUDES IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN HCMC**

Code	Component						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
SF1				0.710			
SF2				0.771			
SF3				0.765			
SF4				0.836			
LF1	0.702						
LF2	0.859						
LF3	0.880						
LF4	0.905						
LF5	0.756						
CP1		0.748					
CP2		0.862					
CP3		0.876					
CP4		0.906					
FF1							0.744
FF2							0.759
FF3							0.681
FF4							0.828
LA1					0.745		
LA2					0.724		
LA3					0.824		
LA4					0.756		
LN1			0.754				
LN2			0.856				
LN3			0.880				
LN4			0.900				
LC1						0.698	
LC2						0.608	
LC3						0.794	
LC4						0.893	

(Source: The authors' processing data and SPSS 22.0)

Table 2 shows the results of EFA. It shows that the independent variable is the student's learning attitude (including LA1 to LA4 with coefficients from 0.724 to 0.824) and 6 dependent variables including: (1) School factor (including SF1 to SF4 with coefficients from 0.710 to 0.836); (2) Lecturer factor (including LF1 to LF5 with coefficients from 0.702 to 0.905); (3) Career prospects (including CP1 to CP4 with coefficients from 0.748 to 0.906); (4) Family factor (including FF1 to FF4 with coefficients from 0.681 to 0.828); (5) Learning needs (including LN1 to LN4 with coefficients from 0.754 to 0.900); and (6) Learners' capacity (including LC1 to LC4 with coefficients from 0.608 to 0.893). Therefore, the proposed content in the study has a coefficient of ≥ 0.5 , which means that the observed variables are statistically significant and meet the set objectives.

FIGURE 3
THE STRUCTURAL MODEL SHOWS THE STRUCTURAL LINKAGE
BETWEEN COMPONENTS

affecting the students' learning attitude in public schools in Ho Chi Minh City meets the research objectives well.

Table 3
COEFFICIENTS FROM TESTING STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODELLING (SEM)

Relationships of components	Unstandardized Coefficient	Standardized Coefficient	C.R.	P	Conclusion
Learning Attitude ← School factor	0.114	0.073	1.551	0.121	H1: Accepted
Learning Attitude ← Lecturer factor	0.039	0.053	1.732	0.103	H2: Accepted
Learning Attitude ← Family factor	0.275	0.071	3.886	***	H3: Accepted
Learning Attitude ← Career prospects	0.015	0.052	2.284	0.043	H4: Accepted
Learning Attitude ← Learning needs	0.068	0.053	1.275	0.202	H5: Accepted
Learning Attitude ← Learners' capacity	0.242	0.069	3.488	***	H6: Accepted

Relationships of components	Unstandardized Coefficient	Standardized Coefficient	C.R.	P	Conclusion
Note: Significant at 1 percent (All t-tests are one-tailed) (Source: The researcher's collecting data and SPSS 22.0, Amos)					

Observing the results obtained in Table 3 shows that:

Hypothesis H1 is accepted: the school factor significantly affects the learning attitude of students in public universities in Ho Chi Minh City (0.114, or 11.4%). The research results show that the rich content of textbooks and library materials has the most influence on the students' learning attitude in public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

Hypothesis H2 is accepted: the lecturer factor significantly affects the students' learning attitude in public universities in Ho Chi Minh City (0.039, or 3.9%). The research results show that the factor of the lecturer providing a lot of material for students to self-study has the most influence on the students' learning attitude in public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

Hypothesis H3 is accepted: the family factor significantly affects the students' learning attitude at public universities in Ho Chi Minh City (0.275 or 27.5%). Research results show that family monitor and timely provide support for children has the most influence on students' learning attitude in public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

Hypothesis H4 is accepted: the factor of career prospects significantly affects the students' learning attitude in public universities in Ho Chi Minh City (0.015 or 1.5%). The research results show that the factor of understanding the position and role of learning in careers is the most influential on the students' learning attitude in public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

Hypothesis H5 is accepted: the factor of learning needs significantly affects the students' learning attitude in public universities in Ho Chi Minh City (0.068, or 6.8%). The obtained research results show that the factor of demand for promotion and high salary in the future has the most influence on the students' learning attitude in public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

Hypothesis H6 is accepted: the learners' capacity significantly affects the students' learning attitude in public universities in Ho Chi Minh City (0.242, or 24.2%). The obtained research results show that the factor of self-study has the most influence on the students' learning attitude in public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

CONCLUSIONS AND MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

Conclusions

The learner's learning attitude is a valuable quality in modern society. Learners with a positive learning attitude will arouse interest. Once learners have interests, it will create a positive awareness in the learning process in general and in specialized subjects in particular. Most of the subject content at the university level is an abstract theory. If the learning process does not have a positive learning attitude, it is challenging to promote creativity in learning. It is also difficult for learners to acquire knowledge. Therefore, a positive learning attitude plays a crucial role in improving the effectiveness of the teaching process.

The objective of this study is to determine the factors affecting the students' learning attitude in public universities in Ho Chi Minh City. The factors are divided into 6 groups: (1) School factors; (2) Lecturer factor; (3) Career prospects; (4) Family factor; (5) Learning needs; and (6) Learners' capacity. The learning attitude is influenced by the six factors. The study has proposed 6 related hypotheses, through analysis, all the proposed hypotheses are accepted. In addition, the analysis results show that with the significance level of $p < 0.05$, there are two factors that greatly affect the attitude of the learners, which are the family factor (affecting the students' learning attitude with the value of 27.5%) and the learners' capacity (affecting the students' learning attitude with the value of 24.2%).

Managerial implications

Through the results of the study of factors affecting students' learning attitude, the authors have the following recommendations:

+ For university

The school factor affecting students' learning attitudes include: Good quality of classrooms; Fully equipped learning equipment for teaching; Safe, healthy and friendly educational environment; Rich textbooks and library materials. In particular, the rich content of textbooks and library materials has a great influence on students' learning attitudes. Therefore, the school needs to invest in equipping necessary facilities and equipment, especially learning books to create the best conditions for training.

Currently, education that is moving towards smart education needs to have modern facilities

integrated with modern scientific and technological achievements. To create quality human resources, the school needs to invest in infrastructure conditions in smart education including diverse and synchronous smart devices based on ICT (smartboard, smart podiums, projectors, tablets,...). In addition, universities in Ho Chi Minh City need to be equipped with surveillance camera systems; school technology systems, broadband Internet connections...

In addition, digital learning content and online learning materials should be made available and assessable with ease; The system of analyzing teaching and learning activities; Extensive, open database and learning resources. The equipment installed in the classrooms includes: Panoramic cameras; Smart interactive whiteboard; Large screen or internally connected TV; Devices that control access based on biological identification; Actuating and controlling devices such as robots, etc., all of which will ensure favourable conditions for the organization of training activities.

Universities should develop criteria and mechanisms to test and evaluate students in the process of participating in learning, encourage students to actively learn through teaching sessions and thematic activities of the industry. In addition, universities should also create a safe, healthy and friendly educational environment. Moreover, they can focus on building a flexible schedule suitable for learners and create favourable conditions for learners in the training process. In particular, the service staff must always provide timely support to students during the training process.

Develop a remuneration regime, encourage lecturers to study and improve their professional qualifications. Develop and effectively implement practical training approaches. Research and develop a master plan on training activities meeting professional standards in long-term, medium-term and short-term periods. Every year, there is a review, supplement and adjustment of training plans and programs to adapt to changes.

+ For teachers

Teachers play an important role in stimulating students' learning attitudes. Therefore, teachers need to guide learners on how to make a study plan to accomplish the tasks set out in the goal. Each individual when developing a specific study plan needs to clearly understand the goal and outline the appropriate steps. When planning, it is necessary to think about what to do to be best prepared to achieve high academic performance and to ask why we do it. This is the process of learning planning, the process of learning how to learn, each individual must project how and when to complete the tasks. In addition, the lecturer must provide a specific teaching plan for each subject so that learners can make a study plan based on that to determine the work students will perform during the process study.

In the process of forming and improving the learning capacity for learners, the role of the teacher is very important. Each lecturer must have a high sense of responsibility in training the young generation and should pay attention to the following points: The lecturer provides a lot of materials for students to self-study; Trainers hone their expertise to gain extensive knowledge; Enthusiastic lecturers create a lively atmosphere in the classroom; Lecturers focus on encouraging and caring for students; Teachers' teaching methods. These are the factors that have a great influence on the students' learning attitude and teachers need to innovate teaching methods according to the requirements to develop quality and competence for learners.

In addition, teachers need to provide students with skills to read textbooks and reference materials. To read books effectively, it is necessary to have a reading method and the reader should comply with the following requirements: Reading with thoughts; Systematic reading; Read selectively; Read with memory; Learn new knowledge by building it up based on what has been learnt. To effectively perceive new knowledge, it is imperative to link old knowledge and other interdisciplinary scientific knowledge as the basis for learners' thinking activities. This skill promotes the process of knowledge perception as well as the active learning of students.

+ For learners themselves

To improve their learning ability, learners need to have a good learning attitude such as being active in learning, which will help learners remember and understand the problem more deeply. Moreover, students need to actively ask themselves questions that will make the brain actively works, once they get the answers it is easier to remember information. Self-discovery and research will help to think faster, and have a positive attitude, which makes learning more interesting.

Learners should be trained to take study as their daily habits. In class, learners have a positive attitude to give arguments so that they can express their thoughts about what they have read, how to apply what they have learned in teaching and life. Readers seek to read other references or exchange what they have collected through discussions with teachers, friends, etc.

Create regular study habits, study habits help learners be self-aware of their learning, not too dependent on the teaching of others. Increasing the ability to find information will help each person consolidate their knowledge deeply and widely in any exercise. Learners actively search on the internet, books or from any other talented, knowledgeable person about what the learner is trying to learn. Learners need to learn in their creative ways, which helps to remember information for a long time and increase learning positivity.

In summary, the above recommendations derived from the assessment of factors affecting students'

learning attitudes, will help students, managers and lecturers to research and find out new ways to improve the quality of teaching and training in universities in general and in public universities in Ho Chi Minh City.

REFERENCES

- Ambrose, M. L. & Kulik, C. T. (1999). Old friends, new faces: Motivation research in the 1990s. *Journal of Management*, Vol. 25 (3).
- Burke, L. & Joanne M. Williams (2008). Developing Young Thinkers: An intervention aimed to enhance children's thinking skills. *Thinking Skills and Creativity* v. 3, pp.104-124.
- Cabrera, A.F., Nora, A. & Castaneda, M.B. 1993, 'College Persistence: Structural equations modelling test of an integrated model of student retention', *Journal of Higher Education*, Vol. 64, No. 2, pp. 123-139.
- Carrol.E.Jzard (1992). *Attitudes of People*, Education Publishing House, Hanoi.
- Cláudia, R., & Filomena V.D. (2012). Families: Influences in Children's Development and Behaviour, From Parents and Teachers' Point of View. *Psychology Research*, ISSN 2159-5542, Vol. 2, No. 12, pp. 693-705.
- Digolo, O. D. (2003). Response to a paper titled: Education Sector Review: How far have we come since independence and what needs to be done to meet education needs of all Kenyans". Paper presented in Education conference, Nairobi. Nairobi: Government Press.
- Dinh, H. T., Hoang, D. T. N., Le T. T. K. (2018). Analysis of factors affecting the results of the study of economics students at Dong Nai university. *Dong Nai university journal*. Vol 11, ISSN 2354 - 1482, pp. 18 - 29.
- Evans, M (1999) *Schools-leavers, Transition to Tertiary Study: A Literature Review*. Working paper no. 3/99. Department of Econometrics and Business Statistics, Monash University, Australia.
- Fredrickson, B. L. (2001). The role of positive emotions in positive psychology: The broadenand-build theory of positive emotions. *American Psychologist*, 56, pp. 218-226.
- Gurpreet Kaur, "Study and Analysis of Lecture Model of Teaching", Vol. 1, India: *International Journal of Educational Planning & Administration*, pp. 9-13, 2011.
- Hair, J., Anderson, R., Tatham, R., & Black, W. (1998). *Multivariate Data Analysis with Readings*. US: Prentice- Hall: Upper Saddle River, NJ, USA.
- Şen, S.H. (2013). The attitudes of university students towards learning. 2nd World Conference on Educational Technology Researches. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 83 (2013) pp. 947 – 953.
- Jenkins, E. W. (1994). Public understanding of science and science education for action. *Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 26, pp.601–612.
- Kara, A. (2010). The Analysis of the Education Student's Attitudes Towards Learning. . 1st National Congress of Education Programs and Teaching, 13-15 May, Balıkesir University (I. Ulusal Eğitim Programları ve Öğretim Kongresi, 13-15 Mayıs, Balıkesir Üniversitesi).
- Kara, A. (2010). The Development Of The Scale of Attitudes Towards Learning. *Elektronik Journal of Social Sciences* .Spring v.9, 32, pp. 049- 062.
- Kharlamop I.F (1979), *How to promote active learning of students*, Education Publishing, Hanoi.
- Laible, D., Carlo, G., Torquati, J., & Ontai, L. (2004). Children's Perceptions of Family Relationships as Assessed in a Doll Story Completion Task: Links to Parenting, Social Competence, and Externalizing Behavior. *Social Development*, 13(4), pp.551–569.
- Le,L.C., Do, T. D., Kieu, N. V. (2020). Factors Affecting Lecturers' Motivation: A Case Study of Public Universities in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam. *Universal Journal of Educational Research* 8(10): pp.4751-4759.
- Mayama, L. (2012). Effects of proprietor Interests on Quality of Education in private secondary schools in Bungoma South District in Kenya. Unpublished M.Ed. Thesis, MasindeMuliro University of Science and Technology.
- Mbatia, P. (2004). *FPE Assessment, Report*. Nairobi: The Jomo Kenyatta.
- Michael Prince. (2004). Does Active Learning Work? A Review of the Research. *Journal of Engineering Education*. V.93 (3), pp.223 – 231.
- Park, C. (2003). Engaging students in the learning process: The learning journal. *Journal of Geography in Higher Education*, 27(2), pp.183-199
- Pekrun, R. (2006). The control-value theory of achievement emotions: Assumptions, corollaries, and implications for educational research and practice. *Educational Psychology Review*, 18,pp. 315-341.
- Pinder, C. C. (1998). *Work motivation in organizational behavior*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- Raditya Ranabumi. (2017). Penggunaan Metode Ceramah Dalam Pembelajaran Menulis Teks Eksposisi Pada Siswa Kelas VII-B Smp Negeri 5 Kediri, *ELIC* pp. 664-669, 2017.

- Relvas, A., & Vaz, C. (2007). Single parenthood: A family a part or part of the family. In A. Relvas, & M. Alarcão (Eds.), *New forms of family* (pp. 253-269). Coimbra: Quartet
- Roeser, R. W., Midgley, C., & Urdan, T. C. (1996). Perceptions of the school psychological environment and early adolescents' psychological and behavioural functioning in school: The mediating role of goals and belonging. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 88(3), pp. 408-422
- Russell, J. A., & Barrett, L. F. (1999). Core affect, prototypical emotional episodes, and other things called emotion: dissecting the elephant. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 76(5), pp.805-819.
- Saban, A. (2000). *Teaching-Learning Process: New Theories and Approaches*. (Öğrenme Öğretme Süreci: Yeni Teori ve Yaklaşımlar). Nobel Publishing. (Nobel Yayın Dağıtım)
- Shaffer, D. (2005). *Developmental psychology: Childhood and adolescence* (). São Paulo: Pioneira Thomson Learning. pp. 60-64.
- Taşpınar, M.(2009). *Teaching Principles and Methods from Theory to Practice* .(Kuramdan Uygulamaya Öğretim İlke ve Yöntemleri). Data Publishing .(Data Yayınları)
- Terenzini, P.T. et al. 1994, 'The Transition to College: Diverse students, diverse stories', *Research in Higher Education*, Vol. 35, No. 1, pp.57-73.
- Weinstein, R. (1998). Promoting positive expectations in schooling. In N. Lambert & B. McCombs (Eds.). *How students learn: Reforming schools through learner-centered education*. Washington, DC: American Psychological Association.
- West, L.H.T. 1985, 'Differential Prediction of First Year University Performance for Students from Different Social Backgrounds', *Australian Journal of Education*, Vol. 29, No. 2, pp. 175-187.
- Xolovaytrich, L.X (1983), *From excitement to talent*, Vietnam Education Publishing House.

Author Information

Lan Chi Le

Saigon University, Vietnam

Thai Dinh Do

Saigon University, Vietnam
